

Adsorbing micellar interface for enhanced removal of lead from aqueous solution

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Abstract : An enhanced removal of lead with polymerized saw dust (PSD) in the presence of micellar solutions of sodium dodecylsulfate (SDS), cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and Criton X-100 has been investigated. The PSD with micellar solution was found to be an effective sorbent for removal of lead from wastewaters in laboratory-scale experiments. Batch studies of PSD with and without micellar systems indicate that Pb removal is greater with micellar systems. The percentage removal of Pb on PSD with micelles increased on decreasing lead concentration and increasing sorbent dose, micellar concentration and electrolyte addition. The single and binary micellar systems also showed marked variations in percentage removal. In single systems of SDS, CTAB and Criton X-100 percentage removal enhancements of lead were 68.5, 65.0 and 3.2% respectively. The binary mixtures of Criton X-100 with SDS and with CTAB enhanced removal upto 74.0% and 69.3% respectively. The combination of SDS and CTAB had no significance effect. The adsorption equilibrium followed Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms. The enhancement in removal was possibly due to interaction between Pb and micellar media and then adsorption on PSD. So, PSD is a good sorbent for both Pb and micelles.

Keywords : Polymerized saw dust (PSD), sodium dodecylsulfate (SDS), cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB).

Introduction

The micellar enhanced removal of lead with sawdust is an efficient removal method for environment safety. It consists of binding of metal ions on a large species (micelle). The effect of electrolytes on the structures and behaviors of the micelles have been extensively studied. The properties of the charged aggregates resulting from counter ion exchanges depend more or less on the involved ions. The implied effects are intricate and no accurate quantitative prediction is available for the structure and behavior of lead solution containing an anionic surfactant sodium dodecylsulfate (SDS), a cationic surfactant cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and a nonionic surfactant iso-octyl phenoxy polyethoxyethanol (Criton X-100). A limited number of studies on sorption of Pb^{II} by various materials have been studied¹⁻⁵. This paper presents suitable operating conditions for the removal of bivalent lead from aqueous solutions using PSD in the absence and presence of micelles of these surfactants.

Experimental

Synthetic lead wastewater :

The stock solution of 1 g/L Pb(NO₃)₂ was prepared. The lead compound was dissolved in limited amount of distilled water and 1.5 mL concn. HNO₃ was added to ensure complete dissolution. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. A series of working standard solutions of 25, 50, 75 and 100 mg/L were made from the stock solution. The pH of working solutions was adjusted to the desired level, sealed and then allowed to stand overnight. The following day pH was readjusted (if necessary) to the desired value and was measured with a pH meter (Systronics) with precision of ±0.05.

Preparation of sorbent :

The sawdust of *Bel (Belae fructus)* wood procured locally was washed with distilled water and dried. It was ground in order to increase the surface area and sieved to 100 mesh size. 2 parts of the sawdust powder was treated with 20 parts of 0.2 N H₂SO₄ and 5 parts of 40% HCHO and was kept in an air oven at 50 °C for 6 h with occa-

sionally stirring. The prepared product was PSD having phenol/HCHO polymeric chain. It was washed several times with distilled water and dried at 60 °C. HCHO polymerized and immobilized the colored water soluble polyphenols¹⁶ from sawdust. The physical and surface properties of PSD determined by the standard methods¹⁷ were surface area 176 m²/g, apparent density 1.40 g/L, cation exchange capacity 1.80 meq/g, ash content 0.07%, pH 6.8 and porosity 0.07 mL/g.

Preparation of micellar media :

SDS and CTAB (from CDH, India with 98% purity) and Criton X-100 (from Qualigens Chemicals, India with 97% purity) were used without no further purification. The stock solution (1 g/L) of SDS, CTAB and Criton X-100 were prepared in distilled water and serial dilutions (10, 20, 40, 60 and 80 mg/L) were made from the stock solution and stored at 4 °C. Each surfactant has a characteristic critical micelle concentration (CMC). The CMC values of SDS, CTAB and Criton X-100 at 20 °C are 8.3×10^{-3} M, 9.2×10^{-4} M and 1.7×10^{-4} M respectively. Stock solutions were prepared every 5 days. Working standards above CMCs were prepared freshly everyday.

Batch studies and analytical methods :

Batch adsorption tests without micelles were performed by shaking PSD with 50 mL aqueous solution of Pb^{II} in a stoppered 250-mL Erlenmeyer flask and then added 1 mL of optimal buffer solution. The contents were continuously agitated at 60 rounds per minute (rpm) in a temperature controlled flask for pre-determined time intervals. This followed centrifugation of the solution for 5 min at 5000 rpm. The supernatant was analyzed for Pb^{II} concentration using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS, Perkin-Elmer 2380). The same procedure was repeated in the presence of micellar media by transferring 50 mL aliquot of Pb^{II} solution + 10 mL micellar solution + PSD in the flask. After shaking, the solution was filtered and then centrifuged when the solution was divided into two phases as surfactant rich phase and aqueous phase. Now the aqueous phase was analyzed using AAS. The quantities of Pb^{II} ions adsorbed on PSD and on PSD +

micelle media were calculated by difference between initial and final concentrations of the solutions.

Results and discussion

Effect of Pb concentrations on removal :

The concentration of Pb^{II} was varied from 25 to 100 mg/L in each batch experiment using PSD (constant dose, 1.0 g/L) + micelle (SDS + Criton X-100 each 80 mg/L in 1 : 1 ratio) at 6.5 pH and 60 °C. The data show a decrease in % removal with rise in the initial concentration of the Pb^{II} in solution. The higher uptake at low concentration can be attributed to the availability of more parking spaces (i.e. active centers) on the surface of adsorbent (saw dust has active sites for both Pb and micelles) for lesser number of adsorbate ions.

Effect of agitation time :

The impact of agitation time on the removal of lead by PSD and PSD + micelle from 50 mg/L Pb^{II} solution using PSD 1.0 g/L, SDS + Criton X-100 (80 mg/L in 1 : 1 ratio), pH 6.5 at 60 °C. The plot of % removal of Pb for various time intervals shows a sudden initial rise in % removal with PSD but not with PSD + micelle. The removal curves are single, smooth and continuous indicating possibility of Pb at outer surface of adsorbent. Equilibrium was attained in about 3 h (it is independent of initial concentration of lead) with PSD but in 1 h with PSD + micelle. It is probably due to the adsorption of Pb at micelle and then micelle and remaining Pb^{II} ions adsorb at the PSD surface.

Effect of pH : The adsorption was studied at different pH values from 2.0 to 9.0. PSD is the most effective at pH 6.0. Above and below this pH, the extent of adsorption of Pb was found to be considerably low. In presence of micelle, with increase in pH from 2.0 to 9.0 marked changes were noticed. The highest lead removal was found at pH 6.0. In the range of the highest sorption efficiency, the dominant species were be Pb²⁺ and Pb(OH)⁺. However, unlike the other metal nitrates, Pb(NO₃)₃ is also incompletely dissociated and species such as Pb(NO₃)₃ may also exist in the solution at pH 6.0–6.5. The re-

Table 1. Effect of lead concentration on removal

Concn. of Pb (mg/L)	% Removal of Pb with PSD	% Removal of Pb with PSD + micelle	% Increase in removal of Pb due to micelle
25	22.2	96.2	74.0
50	16.8	82.4	65.6
75	12.4	70.2	57.8
100	8.7	56.8	48.1

removal of Pb increased significantly with increasing sorbent dose from 0.1 to 1.0 g/L and increasing Pb^{II} concentration from 25 to 100 mg/L. This is because on rising sorbent dose the number of active centres for adsorption of Pb and micelle increases. The surfactant concentration was varied from 10 to 80 mg/L (above CMC). On increasing surfactant concentration micelle size increases due to which more Pb^{II} ions are captured by a micelle. The impact of different surfactants was also studied on 50 mg/L Pb^{II} solution. The total Pb^{II} removals by 100-mesh 1 mg/L PSD in the presence of SDS, CTAB and Criton X-100 were 90.7, 87.2 and 25.4% respectively. The maximum enhancement was recorded with SDS due to its anionic property and cationic species present in lead solution. The difference in enhancement with different surfactants can be explained on the basis of their higher hydrophobicity, electrostatic interaction between the head groups and better packing of their molecules in the micelles. The binary mixtures of three surfactants SDS, CTAB and Criton X-100 were also tried. Increase in Pb removal by Criton X-100 alone was insignificant, but the binary mixtures of SDS and Criton X-100 and of CTAB and Criton X-100 had significant effect on Pb removal. On adding Criton X-100 to SDS or CTAB the removal of Pb increased because Criton X-100 helps to solubilize an ionic surfactant¹⁸.

Effect of electrolyte : An electrolyte such as NaCl had no significant effect on Pb removal in the absence of micelles, but in micellar media on increasing its concentration % removal of lead increased. This is because of the fact that the addition of electrolytes to solutions of ionic surfactants usually increases micelle size and reduces the CMC and hence increase the solubilizing capacity. Non-electrolytes that can be incorporated in the micelle, e.g. alcohol, also favour micelle growth and hence lead to an increase in solubilization.

Effect of temperature : Operating conditions are otherwise similar to those described above. Effects of temperature on lead removal by PSD, PSD + SDS, PSD + CTAB, PSD + Criton, PSD + [SDS + Criton (BN1)] and PSD + [CTAB + Criton (BN2)] were also thoroughly investigated. The increase of temperature from 30 °C to 60 °C increased the sorption of lead indicating the process to be endothermic. The increase in lead adsorption with temperature may be due to the desolvation of the adsorbing species, the changes in the size of pores and enhanced rate of intraparticle diffusion of adsorbate as diffusion is an endothermic process. And % removal increases with increase in temperature due to the increase in solubility of solubilize and of micellar size.

Isotherm parameters :

The adsorption of Pb on PSD was also found to conform to the Freundlich adsorption isotherm at different temperatures

$$\log a = \log K_F + 1/n \log c$$

where c is the equilibrium concentration (mg/L) of Pb^{II} solution and a is the amount of Pb adsorbed per unit mass of PSD (mg/g). The value of the Freundlich constant (K_F) and n at different temperatures were determined from the slopes and intercepts of the linear plots of $\log a$ versus $\log c$ and found to be 0.04 and 1.72; 7.63 and 1.79; 9.31 and 1.83 and 13.09 and 2.03 at 30 °C, 40 °C, 50 °C and 60 °C respectively. The values of n in the range 1–10 represent good adsorption.

The Pb removal by PSD was also analyzed in the light of Langmuir equation. The rearranged (linearized) Langmuir equation may be described as :

$$1/a = 1/Q + 1/Qbc$$

where Q and b are Langmuir constants related to adsorption capacity and energy of adsorption respectively. This equation is usually used to analyze batch equilibrium by plotting $1/a$ versus $1/c$ which yields a linear plot if data conform to the Langmuir isotherm.

The experimental data gave a straight line at each temperature (30 to 60 °C) showing the applicability of Langmuir isotherm. The values of Q and b at varied temperatures were determined from the slopes and intercepts of the plots and are given in Table 2. It clearly shows the formation of monolayer coverage of the sorbate at the outer surface of the sorbent.

Table 2. Isotherm and thermodynamic parameters

Temp. (°C)	Q	b	K_c	ΔG^0 (kJ/mol)
30	120.5	0.022	3.65	-3.23
40	124.0	0.028	4.99	-13.00
50	127.9	0.039	6.44	-17.28
60	134.5	0.056	10.78	-29.88

Conclusions :

The extent of lead removal on PSD increases with increasing sorbent dose and decreasing lead concentration. The maximum removal was found at pH 6.0. After 3 h of contact time the removal ceased. In the presence of SDS, CTAB and Criton X-100 lead removal was enhanced by 68.5, 65.0 and 3.2% respectively. The enhancement of removal was favoured by high micellar concentration, low lead concentration and electrolyte addition. The vol-

ume ratio of lead solution and micellar solution was 5 : 1. The extent of removal was also affected by binary mixtures of micellar media. The micelles from anionic-nonionic binary mixtures of SDS + Criton X-100 enhanced Pb^{II} removal by 74%, whereas cationic + non-ionic mixtures of CTAB + Criton X-100 increased upto 69.3%. Thus it has been concluded that PSD in micellar media become more efficient and may be used to remove Pb from wastewater upto 96.2% under suitable conditions.

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